

INSTITUTIONAL REPOSITORIES : NEED TO IMPLEMENT 5TH LAW OF LIBRARY SCIENCE IN DIGITAL ENVIRONMENT

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Introduction :

The development of ICT coupled with the advent of open source software has brought the massive possibilities for institutions' to establish repositories for archiving intellectual assetsw produced by R &D community,IR captures,preserve and disseminate indivisual institutions intellectual capital in a centralized environment.

History of IR : First discipline based repositories being implemented in the ealy 90s.The key event in the history of IR are-

- 1991: Launch of arXiv physics repository
- 1999: sant fe convention which resulted in the agreement upon a frame work
For archives,now known as Open archive Initiative(OAI)
- 2001: Launch of e-prints by university of Southampton
- 2002 : Publication of Ryam Crows SPARC position paper entiled "The case
For Institutional Repositories : A SPARC position paper.

Institutional Repository

According to SPARC an institutional repository is ' a digital archive of the intellectuals products created by the faculty, research staff,and the students of an institution and accessible by end user both within and outside of the institution with few ,if any barriers to access' (SPARC 2002)

According to Clifford Lynch " university based institutional repository is asset of services that a university university offers to members of the community members" (Lynch,2003)

The IR is a web based service of scholarly material produced by the members of a defined Institute. In short institutional repositories are digital collection that preserve and provide access to the intellectuals of an institute .

Need of Institutional Repository :

1. The bulding of institutional repositories is essential because of the technological changes,increase in research scenario and the increase in demand to access knowledge object from anywhere sy any time.

2. The academic community increasingly recognized the need to store their intellectual output in the form of personal collection.
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4. The academic community felt the need to make available the result of their work within the institution as well as outside the institution, while retaining their digital rights and maintaining their integrity of their work.
5. Institution recognized the need to develop repositories of intellectual output for long term archival purpose.

Objective of Institutional Repository :

1. Intellectual repositories capture the original research and other intellectual property generated by an institution's activity in many fields. In this way, they represent the historical and tangible intellectual assets and output of an institution. According to Wikipedia there are four main objectives.
2. To create visibility for an institution's scholarly research.
3. To collect content in a single location.
4. To provide open access to institutional research output by self-archiving it.
5. To store and preserve other institutional digital assets, including unpublished or otherwise easily lost (gray) literature.

Importance of digital repository :

- Institutional repositories offer seamless access to documents that reflect past and present research interests of the institution as well as its future research goals.
- It makes the publications more usable by contemporary and future scholars as well as other professionals like policymakers and social workers.
- The pace of scholarly communication would be highly accelerated if the IR holds research papers, research reports as soon as they are made public.
- The popularity of this concept is growing rapidly in higher education and research institutions to disseminate newly emerged knowledge and expertise.
- When the institution shares its own knowledge e-resources that not only accelerates knowledge generation and scholarly communication process but also increase its visibility across the nation and international domains.
- IR helps publication in receiving more citations, since the research findings are quickly available to the fellow scholars.

- Institution repository is the marquee of an institution to the world, where institution display its worthwhile research programmes, projects etc to the broad spectrum to audience in the world.

Software Used to create institutional Repository

- A key concept of an IR is the repository management software. Several open source software are available for implementation of IR.
- Dspace
- Eprint
- Greenstone
- Fedora
- Eprint and Dspace are most widely used open source software.

Concept of Institutional Repositories

- Pre-print
- Working papers
- Theses and dissertations
- Research the technical reports
- Conference proceedings
- Departmental and research center news letters and bulletins
- Papers in support of grant application
- Status reports of funding agencies
- Statistical reports
- Technical documentation
- Surveys

Benefits of IR to Academic institutions

- A mean of increasing visibility and prestige; it be used to support making activities to attract high quality staff, student and fundings.
- A mean for centralization and storage of all type of institutional outputs including unpublished literature
- A support tool for learning and teaching
- An aliviation of the requirement to trust publishers to maintain information long term
- A mechanism to keep track and analyse research performance

Benefits of IR to individual Author

- An increase dissemination and impact of scholarship

- Storage and access to a wide range of materials. IR provide greater security and long term accessibility compare to a personal website
- The feedback and commentary, Authors are able to assert priority and receive commentary on pre publication ‘preprints’
- Large scale collaboration
- Flow of information facilities in improve decision making and knowledge transfer creation
- Self arching is a service to scholarship, to the university and the research community
- A central archive of a researches work
- Added value services such as hit counts on papers, personalized publication lists and citation analysis linked cv’s

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